

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF DECEASED DONOR KIDNEY TRANSPLANT AMONG TEACHING HOSPITAL STAFF: IMPLICATIONS FOR LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Background: The scourge of chronic kidney disease (CKD) is alarming and its of significant increasing public health challenge, especially in developing countries. Deceased Kidney transplant (DKT) though not popular, still remains a viable option of treatment. It can reduce the waiting list period for recipients in need of donors. However, there is a palpable gap in knowledge, legal instruments and socio-cultural beliefs which could mitigate against the acceptance of deceased donors in our locals. The study aimed to assess the knowledge and perception of hospital staff about deceased KT. We believe the studied population should have basic knowledge regarding deceased KT. They play a critical role in disseminating awareness to the public about deceased KT in a bid to popularize the practice in our context as most populous African countries.

Methodology: This was a cross-sectional, descriptive study of a teaching hospital staff conducted from November 2023 to February 2024 by applying pretest self-addressed questionnaires, to assess demographic data, knowledge and perceptions of the respondents. The data obtained were analyzed using SPSS version 26 and associations were tested using Pearson's Chi square test while independent predictors of knowledge and perceptions of cadaveric KT were determined by logistic regression.

Results: Two hundred and forty completed electronic questionnaires from the respondents were analyzed. The mean age of respondents was 41.0+/-10.1 with female: male ratio of 2:1. Two hundred and ten (87.5%) knew about brain dead donation while 164 (64.3%) had knowledge about cardiac death donation. Only 176 (74.3%) respondents had strong attitudes towards deceased K.T. Impacts of the cultural and religious beliefs by the respondents were 158 (65.9%) and 192 (80%) respectfully. Forty eight (20%) of the participants were aware of the impending Lagos state legislation on deceased donor KT. Level of education had a P-Value of 0.026 in association with knowledge attitudes and perceptions of deceased KT.

Conclusion: The respondents' knowledge and perceptions of deceased KT were fairly deficient but the awareness of the participants on the legal framework to legislate on deceased KT was non enchanting. This calls for more rigorous policy on enlightenment and effective dissemination of information on the enabling law.

Keywords: Cadaveric kidney transplant, brain dead, cardiac dead, perception, knowledge

Introduction

Kidney transplant still remains the most viable option in the definitive treatment of patients with end stage renal disease (ESRD) because of its great outcome at improving quality of life. The

global burden of death attributed to CKD has been on the increase, to almost 50% since 1997, and has been predicted to be fifth highest cause of years of life lost globally by 2040.¹ The worrisome burden is most impactful in poor region of the world like

Africa where economic-social support base is very meager. To stem or reduce this scourge or mortality, it is therefore imperative to expand KT coverage beyond living related KT in ESRD patients in order to improve their survival. The cadaveric Kidney transplantation is far the commonest type of organ transplantation globally with largest numbers done in the USA and Europe where there are large donor pools, quality facilities, manpower and enabling laws.² Cadaveric kidney transplantation (CKT) is necessary to bridge the gap between demand and supply in countries where there are established programs backed by functioning laws. Organ donation can either be living or deceased depending on the laws of the different states, capacity or awareness. In the USA about 104,000 recipients are waiting for deceased organ of which the majority (90%) are ESRD patients² Conversely, in our locality, the need for KT is more than what's obtainable in the western world even though there is no consensus or updated renal registry.³ There is a palpable concern about limited availability of living donors likewise a growing population of patients on the waiting list for kidney transplant is exponentially alarming. The United States America Organ Procurement Transplant Initiative (USA OPTI) program accounted for one of the largest center for KT and nationally it was noted that about a quarter of wait listed ESRD patients that received a cadaveric KT within 5 years improves outcomes of KT by an increase of 3.4% in year 2022 and OPTI services improved from 14.5 to 73.5%^{4,23}. The deceased donor criteria have been expanded in the western world and this has improved organ donation by nearly 14% in 2021. The donor KT is not yet an active practice in Sub-Saharan Africa with only South Africa and Tunisia having functional cadaveric KT program⁴. The challenges that impede practice of cadaveric KT include the absence of enabling legislation, awareness, cultural values and myth in addition to lack of necessary facilities, adequate financial support and necessary skills. Religious beliefs and socio-cultural superstitions play a significant role in retarding the available donor pool from people who have been declared medically suitable to harvest their kidney on the intensive care unit. Level of education or literacy rate is also a strong factor that determines the attitude of people to

CKT. Illiteracy rate is very high in Sub-Saharan Africa, and could militate against knowledge, acceptability and the potential possibilities of cadaveric organ transplantation.^{4,5,6}

The expectation is that when there is enlightenment through education, a targeted public awareness program in place will engender the right attitude towards acceptance of cadaveric KT and this would culminate into saving more patients with ESRD needing KT. Strong legislation is needed as the starting point for implementing a system for successful cadaveric KT donation. In Nigeria, the Nephrology Association of Nigeria and Transplant Association of Nigeria are currently working on the law with Lagos state Assembly to legislate on guidelines for cadaveric KT program. Awareness and education are key policy points for successful CKT. It is popular opinion that people are more aware of living related kidney transplants (LKT) than the CKT donation.^{7,8,9} The senior health care officers are knowledgeable, familiar and expected to champion the course of the donor KT program by educating the populace about the need to accept deceased donor kidney transplantation. The study therefore aims to assess the knowledge and attitude of the senior teaching hospital staff to deceased donor KT programme and hopes that this research would bridge the knowledge gap among our locals and Africa by extension.

Methods

The study was a cross-sectional, descriptive study conducted at Lagos state University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), Ikeja, Lagos from November 2023 to February 2024. The research was approved by Health Research and Ethic Committee (HREC) of LASUTH. Pre-test self-administered questionnaires were sent out electronically to the senior hospital staff which included the doctors, nurses, pharmacists, laboratory scientists and administrators. These filled and returned questionnaires were assessed for demographic data, knowledge and perceptions of the respondents. The data obtained were analysed using SPSS version 26, associations were tested using Person's Chi square test while independent predictors of knowledge and perceptions of kidney transplant were determined by logistic regression. Power of significant was set at P value less than 0.05

Results

Two hundred and forty respondents who returned the questionnaires were analysed. One hundred and fifty six (65%) were males while eighty four (35%) were female females respectively in ratio 2:1. The age of the respondents ranged from 24-67 years with a mean of 41.0 +/- 10.1 years. Among the responders, one thirty six (56.7%) had post graduate education among which doctors accounted for one hundred and fifty eight (66.0%) while one ninety eight (88.2%) practiced Christianity religion.

Figure 1: Level of awareness on brain-death and cardiac death donor

Regarding knowledge to deceased kidney transplantation, only two hundred and ten (87.5%) of the respondents knew about brain death donation while 164 (64.3%) had knowledge of cardiac death donation. Forty eight (20%) of the respondents were aware of the working of the local law, Lagos State Legislature on impending

deceased donor organ law. In addition one hundred and thirty eight (57.5%) supported that family decision should override the local law on deceased KT, also 59.2% of 240 respondents thought the family of the deceased DKT should be compensated. Regarding attitudes of the respondents to deceased KT, one hundred and seventy six (76.4%) showed readiness to donate and support family members. Respondents whose attitudes were influenced positively by religion and culture were one hundred and fifty eight (65.9%) and one ninety two (80%) respectively. There was a significant association between level of education and gender to knowledge of deceased kidney transplantation ($P < 0.026$ and 0.001) while other sociodemographic variables to knowledge and attitudes were not significant.

Figure 2: Overall attitude towards organ donation

Table 1: Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Variable	Frequency(N=240)	Percentage (%)
Age group (Years)		
≤40	134	55.8
41 - 60	94	39.2
>60	12	5.0
Range	24 - 67	
Mean SD	41.0±10.1	
Gender		
Female	156	65.0
Male	84	35.0
Religion		
Christian	198	82.5
Islam	42	17.5
Marital Status		
Single	46	19.2
Married	182	75.8
Separated/Divorced	8	3.3
Widower	4	1.7
Occupation		
Doctor	158	66.0
ICT	2	0.8
Nurse	56	23.3
Pharmacist	22	9.2
Pharmacist Technician	2	0.8
Level of Education		
Tertiary	104	43.3
Postgraduate	136	56.7
Income		
≤NG300,000	64	26.6
NG300,001 – 500,000	98	40.9
>NG500,000	78	32.5

Table 2: Knowledge of Respondents on Kidney donation and Organ Transplant

Variable	Frequency (N=240)	Percent (%)
Heard of the term kidney donation		
Yes	240	100.0
No	0	000.0
Heard of the term kidney transplantation		
Yes	240	100.0
No	0	000.0
Ever donated an Organ		
Yes	2	0.8
No	136	99.2
Ever received organ for transplantation		
No	240	100.0
Know anyone who has donated an organ		
Yes	94	39.2
No	136	56.7
May be	10	4.2
Know anyone who has received an organ for transplantation		
Yes	178	74.2
No	62	25.8
Know that a donor or recipient can withdraw anytime		
Yes	214	89.2
No	18	7.5
May be	8	3.3

Table 3: Attitude of Respondents towards Kidney donation and Transplant

Variable	Frequency (N=240)	Percent (%)
General Attitude toward donating organ for transplantation		
Strongly Agree	68	28.3
Agree	108	46.0
Neutral	58	24.2
Disagree	4	1.7
Strongly Disagree	2	0.8
General Attitude toward receiving organ for transplantation		
Strongly Agree	72	36.0
Agree	106	48.3
Neutral	48	20.0
Disagree	2	0.8
Strongly Disagree	2	0.8
My religion does not agree with organ donation/transplantation		
Strongly Agree	4	1.7
Agree	4	1.7
Neutral	40	16.7
Disagree	110	45.8
Strongly Disagree	82	34.2
Cultural belief that my body should be kept intact after death		
Strongly Agree	10	4.2
Agree	28	11.7
Neutral	44	18.3
Disagree	88	36.7
Strongly Disagree	70	29.2
Fear that body will be disfigured if I donate my organ		
Strongly Agree	4	1.7
Agree	4	1.7
Neutral	46	19.2
Disagree	116	48.3
Strongly Disagree	70	29.2
Have fear for Surgical Procedures		
Strongly Agree	8	3.3
Agree	82	34.2
Neutral	56	23.3
Disagree	66	27.5
Strongly Disagree	28	11.7
Family does not agree with organ donation		
Strongly Agree	6	2.5
Agree	20	8.3
Neutral	102	42.5
Disagree	72	30.0
Strongly Disagree	40	16.7

Table 4: Perception of Respondents on Kidney donation and Organ Transplant

Variable	Frequency (N=240)	Percent (%)
A donor can be a healthy person		
Yes	226	94.2
No	12	5.0
Not sure	2	0.8
A donor can be a brain-dead person		
Yes	210	87.5
No	18	7.5
Not sure	12	5.0
A donor can be a cardiac-dead person		
Yes	164	68.3
No	46	19.2
Not sure	30	12.5
Aware Lagos Judiciary finalizing legal processing on cadaveric donors		
Yes	48	20.0
No	156	65.0
Not sure	36	15.0
Support the law on deceased donor transplantation		
Yes	182	75.8
No	10	4.2
Not sure	48	20.0
Consent of family of deceased override law on donor transplantation		
Yes	138	57.5
No	68	28.3
Not sure	34	14.2
Think that law should provide that the family of the deceased donor be compensated		
Yes	142	59.2
No	62	25.8
Not sure	36	15.0
Think voluntary deceased donor be compensated		
Yes	152	63.4
No	50	20.8
Not sure	38	15.8
Aware it is illegal to donate your organ for commercial purpose		
Yes	206	85.8
No	24	10.0
Not sure	10	4.2

Table 5: Association between knowledge, Attitude, and demographic characteristics

	Cadaveric (frequency) (%)			Attitude (frequency) (%)		
	Good	Poor	P-value	-ve	+ve	P-value
Age group						
≤40	90(67.2)	44(38.2)	0.206	12(17.9)	55(82.1)	.701
41 - 60	56(59.6)	38(40.4)		7(14.9)	40(85.1)	
>60	10(83.3)	2(16.7)		0(00.0)	6(100.0)	
Gender						
Female	90(57.7)	66(42.3)	0.001*	14(17.9)	64(82.1)	.278
Male	66(78.6)	18(21.4)		5(11.9)	37(88.1)	
Level of Education						
Tertiary	60(57.7)	44(42.3)	0.026*	13(25.0)	39(75.0)	.016*
Postgraduate	96(70.6%)	40(29.4)		6(8.8)	62(91.2)	

Table 6: Logistics regression Model for factors that Predict knowledge and attitude

	Knowledge on cadaveric		COR (95% C.I)	P	AOR (95% C.I)	P
	Good	poor				
Gender						
Male	66	18	2.689(1.461 – 4.950)	0.001*	2.566(1.388 – 4.749)	0.003*
Female	90	66				
Education						
Postgraduate	96	40	1.76(1.030– 3.008)	0.039*	1.631(.943– 2.821)	0.08
Tertiary	60	44				
	Overall Attitude					
	+ve	-ve				
Education						
Postgraduate	62	6	3.444(1.209 – 9.13)	0.021*	2.993(1.012– 8.853)	0.048*
Tertiary	39	13				

OR=Odd Ratio, AOR=Adjusted Odd Ratio, *= Statistically significant, +=positive, -ve =negative, C.I=Confidence interval

Discussion

The astronomical rise in ESRD prevalence and its calamitous outcome in mortality demands an intervention beyond a living related kidney transplant. Deceased KT is gaining more acceptability in most Western parts of the world and this practice has improved donor availability with significant results in reduction in waiting time and quality of lives. In most developing countries, kidney transplantation is majorly by living related donor.¹⁰ However, due to tremendous improvement in organ preservation techniques, deceased donors after brain death and from non-heart-beating patients in intensive care units (ICU) are gradually gaining momentum as a major source of donor for transplantation.¹¹

In the region of Africa, specifically, South Africa still remains the leading centre in Africa in deceased donor KT, while locally, in Nigeria it has never been a practice. The regional variations and dichotomies in acceptability to deceased KT seems to be determined by multiple factors like religion and socio cultural beliefs about death, problems of illiteracy in Africa which limit knowledge and awareness about potential source of deceased organ, lack of technical capacity which include effective immunology laboratory and most importantly paucity of enabling legal framework.^{4,12} This research therefore sets out to assesses the knowledge, attitude and perception to

deceased kidney donors among senior hospital staff who we believe should know better and could be used to convey appropriate knowledge and information about deceased KT to the public.

The present study submitted a mean age of 41.0 ± 10.1 with a range of 24 – 67 years as shown in table 1 which exceeds the mean reported in a similar study done at Sokoto, North west Nigeria and in Indian by Agwu NP et al and Da Silva et al respectively^{13,14} In Nigeria, only living donations are done in her transplantation programme while cadaveric kidney donation is still not a practice due to lack of necessary legislation, logistics and management required to sustain deceased donors KT.¹⁵ In the present study, the majority of the respondents were aware of the deceased donors. These findings correlate with the results obtained in Indian, Ethiopia but not in line with similar studies in Turkey and in Bayelsa state South South Nigeria. The high level of awareness of deceased donors in both studies may be due to the higher level of education of the study participants.^{14,16,17,18} Our study found no significant association between the age of the respondents and the knowledge on deceased donor KT, which runs conversely to the result obtained by Kankam MK.et al who documented that older individual were more likely to be familiar with deceased kidney donor, however, we identify a significant association between the gender and the knowledge

on deceased KT with the odds of 2.566 (95% CI: 1.388 – 4.749) times significantly higher among the females study population as shown in table 6. These findings do not correspond with the findings by Kankam MK et al and a similar study in Nigeria by Anyanwu EG and Obikili EN who noted no significant association between age, gender and knowledge.^{19,20} Our study also reveals that the odds of having good knowledge on deceased donors were 1.76 (1.030 – 3.008) times significantly higher among respondents who had postgraduate level of education. This association was however lost upon adjusting for other factors. In most kidneys transplant regions, major sources of organs for transplantation are patients admitted with brainstem death. The level of awareness of the public regarding brainstem death donors is a major determinant of maximizing organ pool.²¹ In the current study, a vast majority were aware that a donor for kidney transplant could be a brain-dead person and more common than cardiac death donor. This result is in support of the outcomes obtained by Da Silva KX et al but higher than the result obtained in a similar study where 22,6% noted that they were aware of brain-dead donor.^{14,21}

Cadaveric donation programmes are still a subject of legislation in most developing countries. In a study conducted in Turkey, the physicians were reported to have significantly better knowledge about legal aspects of organ donation and transplantation.²² However, in the present study, only 20% were aware of the legislations regarding deceased organ donation as shown in table 4. This vast disparity in both studies is obviously a reflection of the levels of education in the countries where the studies were conducted. Findings from our research reveals that 42,1% had an overall positive attitude towards organ donation which is lower than the findings of Rabiou TB et al where the majority of the population had a positive attitude to deceased donor KT.²¹ We also identify a significant difference between level of education and attitude towards organ donation with the odds of having positive attitude 2.993(95% CI: 1.012– 8.853) times significantly higher among those with postgraduate level of education. Although the level of awareness of deceased donors KT is relatively high yet the overall attitude towards organ donation is abysmally low. This therefore further

reestablished the urgent need to heighten the campaign towards the awareness of deceased organ donation so as to improve the acceptance of the KT program.

Study Limitations

It is a single centre study, in addition some of the staff did not return the questionnaire and this contributed to the fairly low population size.

Conclusion

The the knowledge and attitudes of the senior hospital staff about deceased kidney donations were suboptimal while their responses regarding legal framework was abysmally low in comparison to other regions where deceased donor KT is well practiced. It is therefore imperative to overcome education, legislative, religion and sociocultural barriers that appear to be impedances to effective dissemination of information to the public regarding deceased transplant programmes through policies that enhances effective dissemination of information and enlightenment of the public gears by functional legal framework.

Declarations

Funding

The research did not get any form of funding and we declare no conflict of interests.

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Code availability

Not available

Authors' Contributions

The corresponding authors contrived the topic, designed the methodology and sorted literature search in collaboration with other authors.

Ethics approval

The research was approved by Lagos State University Teaching Hospital Health Research and Ethics Committee (HREC).

Consent to participate

Obtained from participants

Consent for publication

Obtained from participants.

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